

Dehydration-Rehydration Behaviour of Aluminosilicate Hydrogel in Relation to Framework Charge Ratio

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The properties related to the surface area of the hydrogel, viz. adsorption or exchange properties etc. of the heat-treated aluminosilicate hydrogels were primarily dependent on the water content. The nature of dehydration curves was not influenced by framework charge ratio but variation in magnitude was observed at each temperature. No distinct correlation was observed between the magnitude of rehydration and framework charge ratio except a sudden rise in per cent rehydration from 0.44 to 0.42 charge ratio.

IN the zeolite structure, the framework¹ is regarded as the most important unit with cations, small anions and water molecules as constituents. It has already been shown that even solvent has some influence upon the framework structure at the moment of synthesis. A grinding treatment² to a synthetically prepared Na—Y zeolite produces a progressive breakdown of the crystal structure which is due to local overheating of the sample. Mitra *et al.*³ studied the dehydration behaviour of Ni, Co, Mn, Cu, Zn, Cd and Na forms of amorphous synthetic zeolite in the range 70–600°. Mitra and Roy⁴ studied the effect of heat treatment of the synthetic aluminosilicate hydrogel below 200° and found that dehydration was small and there are evidences of gel skeleton collapse at higher temperatures^{3,5,6} followed by large dehydration resulting in a contraction of the channel diameter and a decrease in channel porosity. In the present investigation, equilibrium dehydration loss of aluminosilicate hydrogels having different framework charge ratios were carried out upto 800° and the above heat treated samples were subjected to rehydration at various humidities.

Experimental

Aluminosilicate hydrogel was synthesised following wet interaction process of solution of sodium silicate and sodium aluminate. Aqueous solutions of sodium silicate ($\text{Na}_2\text{O} : \text{SiO}_2 = 1 : 2$) and sodium aluminate ($\text{Na}_2\text{O} : \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 1 : 1$) were used for the synthesis. The specific gravity of stock solutions was 1.6. Both the stock solutions were diluted 25 times at the time of preparation at room temperature to achieve best results. The gels prepared were washed free of alkali, dried and ground to $-20+50$ mesh and were incubated at $32 \pm 1^\circ$ in accordance with the procedure followed by Mitra *et al.*⁴. The ratios of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{SiO}_2$ in the batch compositions were kept at 10 : 1, 6 : 1,

4 : 1, 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 4, 1 : 6 and 1 : 10, respectively.

Equilibrium dehydration–rehydration was studied by following the previous procedure⁵. Each sample (2 g) taken out from the incubator, was placed in a platinum crucible and heated in an electrically heated muffle furnace at the selected temperature for 3 h as it was experimentally observed that even at 100° the equilibrium dehydration is attained within 2 h. After determining the weight loss, the heat-treated samples were successively equilibrated for 24 h in a rehydration chamber at relative humidities of 17, 35, 56 and 100% weighed after each stage and finally placed in the incubator ($32 \pm 1^\circ$). All the weighings were carried out on a single pan balance having an accuracy of 0.0001 g and as such the error arising out of weighings was negligible. In addition to it, the time lag between the removal of the sample after dehydration and placement in the rehydration chamber was kept same in all the equilibrium dehydration and rehydration experiments in order to have comparable results.

Results and Discussion

The aluminosilicate hydrogel as synthesised under present experimental conditions, was amorphous in nature as evidenced by X-ray analysis (Fig. not shown). The framework charge ratio of the synthesised aluminosilicate hydrogels was calculated from $\text{Al}/(\text{Al}+\text{Si})^7$. In the present investigation, there was wide variation of this ratio, *i.e.* from 0.22 to 0.66 although the batch composition was also varied to a wider extent. Equilibrium dehydration curves obtained by plotting equilibrium dehydration as a function of temperature of heat treatment have been shown in Fig. 1 and the results are given in Table 1. The nature of the curves was not influenced by framework charge ratio but

Fig. 1.

differences in the magnitude of dehydration were observed at each temperature. The dehydration curves were not continuous in nature but proceeded in steps, *i.e.* upto 100° the rate was fairly slow followed by a sharp rise upto 200° and then again slowed down. In the present investigation, the exchangeable cation was not varied but the magnitude of charge and their distribution in the anionic framework differed according to the molar ratio

Fig. 2.

varied directly with the temperature of heat treatment, indicating thereby that the intensity of interaction of the water molecules associated with the

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM DEHYDRATION LOSS OF ALUMINOSILICATE HYDROGELS HAVING DIFFERENT FRAMEWORK CHARGE RATIOS ON PROGRESSIVE HEAT TREATMENT

Framework charge ratio	Ratio of $Al_2O_3 : SiO_2$	Percent dehydration on heat treatment (°C)									
		70	100	150	200	300	400	500	600	700	800
0.66	10 : 1	5.52	6.28	15.26	16.53	17.72	18.48	19.63	20.28	20.74	21.89
0.60	6 : 1	5.24	5.52	14.64	15.42	17.27	17.99	18.81	19.27	20.22	20.92
0.57	4 : 1	5.05	5.36	13.84	15.10	16.73	17.63	18.93	19.11	20.02	20.90
0.50	2 : 1	5.20	5.31	13.84	14.97	16.41	17.26	18.13	18.86	19.29	19.99
0.44	1 : 1	4.63	5.15	13.82	14.50	16.20	17.13	17.67	18.82	18.96	19.94
0.42	1 : 2	4.36	5.26	13.94	13.99	15.93	17.40	17.89	18.18	18.29	19.76
0.40	1 : 4	4.22	4.28	12.28	13.28	15.20	16.80	16.92	17.77	17.91	19.25
0.33	1 : 6	3.88	4.12	12.99	13.96	14.76	15.26	15.78	16.02	17.02	18.78
0.22	1 : 10	3.02	3.76	11.32	12.91	13.36	14.40	14.62	16.12	16.56	17.21

of $Al_2O_3 : SiO_2$ in the composition. It may be observed that in all cases, about 80% dehydration was completed at 300°. The magnitude of dehydration followed a direct relationship with the framework charge ratio and thus linear relationship was observed at each temperature. Because of similar nature, some graphs are shown in Fig. 2. It can be observed from the curves that the slope

gel structure was a direct function of temperature. The samples were dehydrated at each temperature for 3 h, weighed and were immediately placed successively in the rehydration chamber at four different humidities, *viz.* 17, 35, 56 and 100% and the results are shown in Tables 2-5.

The common relationship observed in the rehydration study were as follows: (i) in each case,

TABLE 2—EQUILIBRIUM REHYDRATION OF DEHYDRATED ALUMINOSILICATE HYDROGEL HAVING DIFFERENT FRAMEWORK CHARGE RATIO ON PROGRESSIVE HEAT TREATMENT

Framework charge ratio	Percent rehydration on dehydration on heat treatment 17% RH at (°C)									
	70	100	150	200	300	400	500	600	700	800
0.66	15.58	15.06	12.62	6.02	5.67	4.98	4.36	4.10	3.15	0.38
0.60	15.87	15.02	12.20	5.82	4.75	4.13	3.49	3.36	2.06	0.66
0.57	14.91	14.52	11.42	5.68	4.44	3.46	3.22	3.06	2.29	0.54
0.50	13.69	13.11	10.44	5.09	4.05	3.16	2.64	2.60	2.31	0.31
0.44	13.42	13.00	10.33	4.81	3.75	2.11	1.88	1.84	1.75	0.42
0.42	15.75	15.14	12.57	5.97	4.76	4.14	3.25	3.08	2.78	0.58
0.40	14.18	13.78	11.69	5.62	4.22	4.04	3.66	3.26	1.81	0.36
0.33	14.28	13.62	10.84	4.92	4.04	3.05	2.78	2.11	2.01	0.82
0.22	13.90	13.61	10.99	5.28	4.11	2.84	2.77	2.52	1.05	0.62

TABLE 3—EQUILIBRIUM REHYDRATION OF DEHYDRATED ALUMINOSILICATE HYDROGELS HAVING DIFFERENT FRAMEWORK CHARGE RATIOS ON PROGRESSIVE HEAT TREATMENT

Framework charge ratio	Percent rehydration on dehydration on heat treatment at 35% relative humidity at (°C)									
	70	100	150	200	300	400	500	600	700	800
0.66	23.28	22.42	18.58	9.59	8.06	7.15	6.34	6.08	5.89	1.65
0.60	23.18	22.26	17.92	8.24	7.88	7.05	6.81	6.58	4.40	1.70
0.57	23.15	22.51	16.71	8.67	6.92	6.37	5.99	5.88	4.71	1.49
0.50	22.13	22.00	15.34	7.73	6.38	5.59	5.23	5.17	5.05	1.12
0.44	21.60	20.96	15.26	7.95	5.18	4.25	3.93	3.92	3.67	1.18
0.42	23.38	22.59	18.30	9.40	7.52	7.09	6.33	6.31	5.20	1.82
0.40	21.26	20.34	15.32	7.28	5.28	5.18	4.46	4.35	3.59	1.12
0.33	22.23	21.27	15.01	7.53	5.43	5.04	4.98	4.19	3.87	1.39
0.22	22.71	21.89	15.93	8.15	5.93	5.16	5.12	4.88	1.38	1.20

TABLE 4—EQUILIBRIUM REHYDRATION OF DEHYDRATED ALUMINOSILICATE HYDROGELS HAVING DIFFERENT FRAMEWORK CHARGE RATIOS ON PROGRESSIVE HEAT TREATMENT

Framework charge ratio	Percent rehydration on dehydration on heat treatment at 56% relative humidity at (°C)									
	70	100	150	200	300	400	500	600	700	800
0.66	25.12	24.92	19.52	10.62	9.89	9.35	8.41	8.11	8.01	3.24
0.60	24.66	23.81	19.74	10.28	9.64	9.21	8.60	8.57	5.79	1.93
0.57	24.76	23.64	18.08	9.50	8.53	8.20	7.72	7.62	6.26	3.70
0.50	23.22	22.41	16.45	8.05	7.60	7.23	6.80	6.67	6.62	4.40
0.44	23.48	22.52	16.13	8.09	6.44	5.84	5.34	5.24	5.15	2.30
0.42	25.73	22.56	20.07	10.51	9.53	9.32	8.47	8.41	6.31	3.38
0.40	23.72	23.18	16.76	8.21	4.67	7.52	7.02	6.80	4.30	2.58
0.33	23.98	23.20	16.10	8.72	6.48	6.18	6.01	5.95	4.43	3.12
0.22	24.03	23.89	17.18	9.63	7.11	6.42	6.34	5.77	2.21	1.78

TABLE 5—EQUILIBRIUM REHYDRATION OF DEHYDRATED ALUMINOSILICATE HYDROGELS HAVING DIFFERENT FRAMEWORK CHARGE RATIOS ON PROGRESSIVE HEAT TREATMENT

Framework charge ratio	Percent rehydration on dehydration on heat treatment at 100% relative humidity at (°C)									
	70	100	150	200	300	400	500	600	700	800
0.66	37.60	37.41	36.65	28.42	27.72	26.52	25.82	24.97	23.98	20.52
0.60	43.05	42.64	38.20	25.78	25.07	24.36	24.18	22.50	19.30	17.77
0.57	35.98	35.27	35.04	23.29	23.11	22.42	21.24	17.58	16.52	10.99
0.50	32.59	32.41	30.74	19.97	19.30	19.09	18.68	15.93	14.67	13.39
0.44	25.31	24.84	23.24	15.49	14.50	13.42	12.64	12.00	11.41	8.27
0.42	35.28	35.00	34.72	30.02	29.89	26.72	25.95	22.58	20.57	16.32
0.40	33.67	33.14	31.70	22.89	20.23	19.71	18.71	15.23	13.96	12.76
0.33	26.51	26.12	25.99	15.91	15.82	13.97	13.82	13.17	12.47	12.39
0.22	36.57	35.68	34.75	18.65	18.59	15.41	14.52	14.34	13.98	10.98

rehydration was found to be a direct function of temperature of heat treatment, (ii) the rehydration was inversely related to the temperature of heat treatment, and (iii) the framework charge ratio was found to exhibit virtually no influence on the nature of the rehydration.

The inflection remained the same in all the cases, *i.e.* from 150 to 200°, a rapid decrease of rehydration capacity was noticed followed by very slow rate of rehydration on further heat treatment. The abnormally high increase in adsorption capacity during rehydration of the gels than the original water content is related to the humidity and lattice flexibility of the structure of the gel. At saturated humidity, the retentivity of porous structure was observed through moisture adsorption although the magnitude decreased sufficiently. At super saturation (100% R_H), there may not be total adsorption but certain amount of condensation of water vapour may also be possible, and hence abnormal increase in the percentage rehydration. Maximum and minimum rehydration was noticed with the samples having framework charge ratio 0.66 and 0.44, respectively. The lower percentage of rehydration at lower relative humidity (R_H) may be due to inadequate amount of water vapour available for rehydration as the percent rehydration may become the same if an adequate amount of exposure in a free atmosphere of lower relative humidity is allowed. It may be mentioned that as the exchangeable cation remained the same in all the samples,

the nature of cationic water remained unaltered but the sites of the exchangeable cations only may be modified by heat treatment. Moreover, heat treatment may also cause change in the pore structure of the aluminosilicate gels, which may reflect the adsorption capacity of the gels.

Conclusion : Linear relationship was observed when the amount of dehydration was plotted against framework ratio at each temperature of dehydration. Although no distinct correlation was observed between the magnitude of rehydration and framework charge ratio, there was a sudden rise in percentage rehydration from 0.44 and 0.42 charge ratio. Rehydration was found to be a direct function of humidity and inversely related to the temperature of heat treatment.

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